

MEANINGS OF PHASES WITHIN THE STRUCTURE OF THE SEMANTICS

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Annotation

The article presents the presence of special phase verbs as well as verbs that embody the semantics of phase provide evidence that the phase is a distinct stage in the progression of the process. This is supported by the fact that special phase verbs are used. During the process, there are often three stages that are distinguished: the initial phase, the continuation phase, and the end phase. Changes in the meanings of these phases are due to the syntactic environment of the phase and relevant verbs. The core of aspectuality is intimately connected to the concept of phase.

Key words: phase, phase lexemes, phase characteristics, phasic verbs, sema, phase values, actant, phase values "begin," "continue," and "stop".

The modern English vocabulary for phase allows for the expression of multiple nuances of meaning, depending on what the subject of the utterance brings to the table in terms of characterizing the phase situation. The lexical method of transferring phase values is given a lot of attention in this study that we have written. The separation of an activity into distinct phases is linked to a variety of semantic properties, including continuity, integrity, limit, iteration, discontinuity, and renewal in addition to the beginning and the conclusion of an event. When the question is phrased in such a way, the dynamics of action are considered from two different points of view: ontological, which reflects the true character of the activity, and subjective, which is the product of reflection of this action in human thinking and perception. Both of these points of view are taken into consideration.

The study of aspectology has improved in terms of its pragmatic application as a result of the classifications of semantic categories of predicates that are known in modern linguistics. However, the presence of these components of meaning inside the semantic structure of the meanings of verbs is not the only factor that determines the meaning of a verb. Verbs can be categorized into a variety of distinct groups depending on the sense that is being taken into account [8,47].

The phase vocabulary is a more expressive way of communication. Linguists classify it as semi-auxiliary, auxiliary, and combative, and it fulfills the roles of operators, modifiers, and secondary predicates. As a result of their semantics, phase verbs are capable of conveying all nuances of the semantic categorization of the action, and they can be paired with any kind of predicate.

The existence of a merging border between the meanings that are communicated by phase lexemes and the dependent syntactic forms of significant verbal predicates that denote the actual action or process is an important aspect to take into consideration. Phasic verbs are typically denied independence at both the semantic and syntactic levels of the phrase, as you

are aware. However, in the framework of discourse, their role expands, and it becomes possible for them to define the meaning of the entire assertion. This occurs when the "FG + complement" complex is broken, or when the action that was launched does not progress into the level of implementation of the "core" (to borrow an expression from A. Freed). It is possible to make reference to cases that have been cited in this relation, such as "He began to sneeze, but did not sneeze" with the verb "start" [5,69].

In light of the previous, it would be beneficial to do research on the characteristics of the semantic organization of sentences that are reflected in the distribution model N 1 V pr. N 2. Because the verb possesses valence properties, the presence of the nominal actant N 2 is required for the sentence to be structurally and semantically complete. This requirement arises from the fact that the N 2 is a nominal actant. As a result of the nature of its status, this nominal actant performs the role of a prepositional object. A noun that has both a subject and an abstract meaning can be used to denote this category of object.

In accordance with the rules of grammar, a noun that does not have a specific meaning can have the same syntactic potential as a term that have a meaning. Their singularity lies in the fact that they represent an autonomous substance while denoting activities, occurrences, situations, or signs. The preposition in the preceding phrase fulfills the role of a subordinating syntactic connection, maintains a close connection with the verb, and contributes to the creation of subject-object relations through the lexical meaning it conveys. The organization of the meaning of the sentence's semantics is somewhat complicated, and the structure of the proposition serves as its foundation.

Grammatical theories have, for a very long time, distinguished completely significant verbs from non-significant verbs by categorizing verbs into either of these two categories. Auxiliary verbs are distinguished from ordinary verbs because they perform a function that is dependent on another verb rather than acting on their own. Examples of auxiliary verb classes include phase, modal, and a few more.

There is a sema of phase in the meaning of phase verbs, which refers to the phase of the process. Through careful examination of the supporting evidence, it was possible to identify three primary categories of phase values. For instance, the presence of the corresponding phase sema is the need for classifying something as belonging to the phase field of the beginning:

After that, Mr. Frank Dadds began delivering his remarks. (J. Priestly) He prepared himself for hard work by rolling up his sleeves. (The Grisham Novels).

One of the characteristics of the examples of sentences that we are looking at is the fact that verbs in these phrases are able to realise both of their valences at the syntactic level. On the other hand, the structure of the sentence only contains one subject argument, which serves the function of both the subject and the predicate. The semantic core of the predicate is referred to as an abstract prepositional object, and the verb fulfils the role of another component of the predicate known as a verbalizer and a carrier of the phase sema in the sentence.

For comparisons Let us now focus our attention to the sentence. Brush got intrigued by the dramatic spectacle of so many challenges being faced by a single individual. (T. Wilder) This is an excellent illustration of a different kind of phase verb, which is a classic example. The combination of the phase verb become and the causative verb fascinate is part of the causative situation and comprises its predicate; hence, it is sufficient from a semantic point of

view. Abstract prepositional objects such as spectacle and disadvantages, which each represent a complex set of indicators of a particular circumstance, perform the semantic role of the emotional state's causal agent by being articulated as part of a predicative complex that has a meaning associated with a phase. The argumentative position held by the abstract complement in reference to the main phase predicate can be deduced from the fact that the passive construction (its transform) was used. In the remaining examples, such a transformation is shown to be impossible, which suggests that abstract terms that perform the role of a core have a distinct semantic function.

The continuation or the length of an action or process is covered by the second phase field, which contains the following:

The young woman was diligent in her work. (J. Steinbeck)

The remainder of the day consisted of the usual schedule of classes for him to attend. (B. Steiner)

The following suggestions pertain to the third phase field, which is the procedure of the last phase: Bill's drinking has moved far beyond the stage where it was socially acceptable. (J. Updike)

However, Miss Pinkerton had arrived at a decision really quickly. (M. Spark)

When abstract prepositional objects are used with verbs that express the meaning of a phase, their functioning demonstrates that in a variety of contexts, they exhibit a weakening of the lexical meaning that they are associated with. In this context, these verbs transmit the meaning of the beginning, continuation (duration), or end of an action or process; acting in an ambiguous sense, verbs in their set, along with phase ones, can also have other meanings. In this way, the verbs convey the meaning of the beginning, continuation (duration), or end of an activity or process.

Although it holds a leading position, the phase value could be relegated to a lower position in the hierarchy of values. For instance, the verb "keep" functions as an instantiator for the phase. Verbs whose meanings include phases can serve as units for quantification of predicates. Phasic verbs are verbs that can be used to indicate a specific stage of an activity or process that is related to the past, the present, or the future.

The study of the semantics, syntax, and pragmatics of phase vocabulary in modern English reveals rich opportunities for conveying subtle differentiations in the articulation of various types of predicates and enables us to expand our understanding of the arsenal of expressive means in the field of conveying phase meanings. This study also indicates rich opportunities for conveying rich opportunities for conveying subtle differentiations in the articulation of various types of predicates [2,45].

In many situations where these verbs are used, it is common practice to refer to the phase values "begin," "continue," and "stop" that match the meanings of the verbs that correspond to them. This is done out of habit. The meaning of "begin" is the most fundamental component of the system that phase values form, and it is also the most fundamental. How derivative can the meaning of "cease," which is viewed as "start not," and the meaning of "continue," which is interpreted as how to "not stop" be? [6,22]. The meaning of "cease" is interpreted as "start not," and the meaning of "continue" is interpreted as how to "not stop."

There is a connection between the idea of phase values and the functional semantic field. In turn, the idea of FSF phase is made up of three different parts, each of which can be

interpreted as an expression of a different level of phase. The first component is comprised of semantic classes of predicative words (verbs) that are combined with phase meanings; the second component is comprised of lexico-grammatical, grammatical, and contextual means that are used to some extent to express phase values; and the third component is comprised of words and phrases that lexically express phase values and are correspondingly combined with the semantic classes of verbs, which form the first component of the FSP [1, 154].

If we accept that the phase values correspond to the stages of an action that flows across time, then it is clear what verbs can be used to communicate this meaning because they denote actions that are temporally localized and, due to the very nature of the actions, can be paused and restarted. The conclusion that can be drawn from this is that the verbs that signify constant qualities and ratios are almost never coupled with phase values. However, it's important to keep in mind that action verbs have a few quirks. There are two distinct types of acts that might be considered to be localized in time. There are some actions that do not actually take a certain amount of time. They are performed "in one movement" and are typically stated with the assistance of so-called one-act verbs like jump, fall, and appear. The timing of their occurrence is tied to the time of the moment. [3,168].

The execution time of other acts is a segment that can be plotted on the time axis and which, as a result, defines a particular period of validity. This is because the execution time is an interval. Consequently, the following is an illustration of the first possible form of the sentence: The youngster was knocked from the chair, and the following is an illustration of the second: The young lady was out and about in the neighborhood.

The stages, which are typically referred to as phases, are only able to be identified for temporally localized continuous actions, and as a result, these actions are combined with phase values: The boy either started, stopped, or is still going around the tree in a running circle.

In the group of formation phase verbs denoting the beginning, continuation and end of any action, the main ones are *start*, *stop*, *continue*. Analogues of these verbs in language are *to begin*, *to continue*, *to stop* and in Uzbek *boshlamoq*, *davom ettirmoq*, *tugallamoq*. We can say that these verbs are neutral, display the phase characteristics in their purest form and are combined with any verbs denoting a continuous localized in time action.

It is impossible to restrict the phase feature of verbs to just three representatives in each language. Due to the widespread use synonymous units phase value can also be passed in Uzbek language with such verbs as *bo'lmoq*, *qabul qilmoq*, *davom etmoq*, *yo'lga chiqmoq*, *shoshilmoq*, *bormoq*, *odatlanmoq*, *boshlamoq*, *to'xtamoq*, *chiqmoq*, *tugatmoq*, *yakunlamoq*, (with negation or circumstance *bundan tashqari*, *ko'proq*), *to'xtamang*, *davom etmoq*, *qolmoq* shakllarida uchraydi. [1,267]

The English language has a certain number of verbs, having phase characteristics: *to begin*, *to start*, *to initiate*, *to activate*, *to finish*, *to end*, *to stop*, *to conclude*, *to terminate*, *to halt*, *to continue*, *to proceed*, *to prolong*, etc. It should be noted the huge potential of phrasal verbs of the English language, a considerable part of which has a phase value: *to keep up*, *to go on*, *to give up*, *to wind up*, *to set about*, *to kick off*, *to carry on*, *to fetch up*, *to go along* and others. In this case, the verbs get new phase value by particle attachment means.

In turn, English phasic verbs also have some vocabulary traits that are unique to them. To begin, the construction of new verbs, especially phrasal verbs, is a common application of

the prefix when it comes to English word formation. By joining the basis of the prefix verb is formed by the unique meaning of the verb: *to plant, install; to begin; ride; continue*, etc. Secondly, in a number of cases, phase values are formed by means of attaching a noun, particle or preposition to a verb: *finish - come to the end, put an end, start- going on, get on with it*.

Therefore, verb units are a productive way of updating phase values in all of the Uzbek and English languages that have been mentioned.

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